

PCT neon - cut-off < 2

Study	TP	FP	FN	TN	Cut-off	Timing	Onset	Sensitivity (95% CI)	Specificity (95% CI)
Zahedpasha 2009	11	20	0	7	0.5	T0	Early+Late	1.00 [0.72, 1.00]	0.26 [0.11, 0.46]
Naher 2011	9	18	1	22	0.5	T0	Early+Late	0.90 [0.55, 1.00]	0.55 [0.38, 0.71]
Boo 2008	16	41	2	28	0.5	T0	Early+Late	0.89 [0.65, 0.99]	0.41 [0.29, 0.53]
Adib 2012	14	29	6	20	1.15	T0	Early+Late	0.70 [0.46, 0.88]	0.41 [0.27, 0.56]
Lopez Sastre 2006	50	8	11	31	0.59	T0	Late	0.82 [0.70, 0.91]	0.79 [0.64, 0.91]
Vazzalwar 2004	14	12	4	21	1.0	T0	Late	0.78 [0.52, 0.94]	0.64 [0.45, 0.80]

PCT neon - cut-off = 2/2.5

Study	TP	FP	FN	TN	Cut-off	Timing	Onset	Sensitivity (95% CI)	Specificity (95% CI)
Resch 2003	34	10	7	17	2.0	T0	Early	0.83 [0.68, 0.93]	0.63 [0.42, 0.81]
Guibourdenche 2002	18	9	3	79	2.5	T0	Early	0.86 [0.64, 0.97]	0.90 [0.81, 0.95]
Koskenvuo 2003	5	14	0	3	2.0	T12	Early	1.00 [0.48, 1.00]	0.18 [0.04, 0.43]
Schlapbach 2013	29	51	4	53	2.0	T24-72	Early	0.88 [0.72, 0.97]	0.51 [0.41, 0.61]
Boo 2008	16	24	2	45	2.0	T0	Early+Late	0.89 [0.65, 0.99]	0.65 [0.53, 0.76]
Zahedpasha 2009	11	18	0	9	2.0	T0	Early+Late	1.00 [0.72, 1.00]	0.33 [0.17, 0.54]
Groselj-Grenc 2009	14	15	3	14	2.28	T0	Early+Late	0.82 [0.57, 0.96]	0.48 [0.29, 0.67]
Sakha 2008	18	45	9	45	2.5	T0	Early+Late	0.67 [0.46, 0.83]	0.50 [0.39, 0.61]

PCT neon - cut-off > 2.5

Study	TP	FP	FN	TN	Cut-off	Timing	Onset	Sensitivity (95% CI)	Specificity (95% CI)
Bender 2008	20	31	9	63	5.75	T0	Early	0.69 [0.49, 0.85]	0.67 [0.57, 0.76]
Resch 2003	32	2	9	24	6.0	T0	Early	0.78 [0.62, 0.89]	0.92 [0.75, 0.99]
Bonac 2000	5	9	4	40	9.98	T0	Early	0.56 [0.21, 0.86]	0.82 [0.68, 0.91]
Zahedpasha 2009	10	4	1	23	10.0	T0	Early+Late	0.91 [0.59, 1.00]	0.85 [0.66, 0.96]
Boo 2008	13	17	5	52	10.0	T0	Early+Late	0.72 [0.47, 0.90]	0.75 [0.64, 0.85]
Groselj-Grenc 2009	5	0	11	29	5.55	T24	Early+Late	0.31 [0.11, 0.59]	1.00 [0.88, 1.00]

